

Comparison and evaluation of sampling and eDNA metabarcoding protocols to assess soil biodiversity in Belgian LUCAS Biopoints: supplementary information

EJP Soil WP6. Task 6.3: Double sampling exercise, part B. Soil Biodiversity assessment

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Table S1. Sample metadata (from left to right): location, protocol name, detailed protocol name, soil depth, land-use category, EUNIS (European Nature Information System) code, and LUCAS-ID.

Sample	Location	Protocol	Protocol2	Sampling depth (cm)	Land-use	EUNIS	LUCAS-ID
Bredene_0_10	Bredene	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Cropland	V1	38363148
Bredene_10_30	Bredene	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Cropland	V1	38363148
Bredene_Lucas	Bredene	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Cropland	V1	38363148
Burdinne_0_10	Burdinne	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Cropland	V1	39203098
Burdinne_10_30	Burdinne	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Cropland	V1	39203098
Burdinne_Lucas	Burdinne	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Cropland	V1	39203098
Cerfontaine_0_10	Cerfontaine	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Grassland	R1	39203022
Cerfontaine_10_30	Cerfontaine	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Grassland	R1	39203022
Cerfontaine_Lucas	Cerfontaine	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Grassland	R1	39203022
Deurne_0_10	Deurne	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Grassland	R1	39343134
Deurne_10_30	Deurne	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Grassland	R1	39343134
Diepenbeek_0_10	Diepenbeek	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Forest	T1	40003102
Diepenbeek_10_30	Diepenbeek	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Forest	T1	40003102
Diepenbeek_Lucas	Diepenbeek	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Forest	T1	40003102
Diepenbeek_forest_floor	Diepenbeek	INBO	Forest floor	Forest floor	Forest	T1	40003102
Genappe_0_10	Genappe	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Cropland	V1	39303074
Genappe_10_30	Genappe	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Cropland	V1	39303074
Genappe_Lucas	Genappe	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Cropland	V1	39303074
Gon_0_10	Gontrode	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Forest	T1	NA
Gon_10_30	Gontrode	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Forest	T1	NA
Gontrode_forest_floor	Gontrode	INBO	Forest floor	Forest floor	Forest	T1	NA
Herentals_0_10	Herentals	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Grassland	R1	39623132
Herentals_10_30	Herentals	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Grassland	R1	39623132
Marke_0_10	Marke	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Forest	T1	38443098
Marke_10_30	Marke	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Forest	T1	38443098
Marke_Lucas	Marke	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Forest	T1	38443098
Molenbeek_0_10	Molenbeek	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Recreation	V2	39783064
Molenbeek_10_30	Molenbeek	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Recreation	V2	39783064

Molenbeek_Lucas	Molenbeek	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Recreation	V2	39783064
Seneffe_0_10	Seneffe	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Grassland	R1	39123062
Seneffe_10_30	Seneffe	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Grassland	R1	39123062
Seneffe_Lucas	Seneffe	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Grassland	R1	39123062
Sombreffe_0_10	Sombreffe	INBO	INBO_0_10	0_10	Cropland	V1	39383058
Sombreffe_10_30	Sombreffe	INBO	INBO_10_30	10_30	Cropland	V1	39383058
Sombreffe_Lucas	Sombreffe	LUCAS	LUCAS	0_30	Cropland	V1	39383058

Table S2. Overview of all Annelida taxa detected using the Annelida-specific primers (Olig01). Empty cells inherit taxonomic classification from above; dash (-) represents unresolved identification.

Order	Family	Genus	Species	
Crassicitellata	Lumbricidae	<i>Allolobophora</i>	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	
		<i>Aporrectodea</i>	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea icterica</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea limicola</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea nocturna</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	
			<i>Aporrectodea sp h1</i>	
			-	
			<i>Bimastos</i>	<i>Bimastos rubidus</i>
			<i>Dendrobaena</i>	<i>Dendrobaena octaedra</i>
			<i>Eisenia</i>	-
			<i>Eiseniella</i>	<i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i>
			<i>Lumbricus</i>	<i>Lumbricus castaneus</i>
				<i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>
				<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>
		<i>Satchellius</i>	<i>Satchellius mammalis</i>	
Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Achaeta</i>	<i>Achaeta bifollicula</i>	
			<i>Achaeta bohemica</i>	
			<i>Achaeta unibulba</i>	
			-	
			<i>Buchholzia</i>	<i>Buchholzia appendiculata</i>
				<i>Buchholzia fallax</i>
				-
			<i>Cernosvitoviella</i>	-
			<i>Chamaedrillus</i>	-
			<i>Cognettia</i>	<i>Cognettia chlorophila</i>
			<i>Enchytraeus</i>	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>
				<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>
				<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>

			<i>Enchytraeus dicaetus</i>
			<i>Enchytraeus lacteus</i>
			<i>Enchytraeus norvegicus</i>
			-
		<i>Enchytronia</i>	<i>Enchytronia parva</i>
			-
		<i>Fridericia</i>	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>
			<i>Fridericia christeri</i>
			<i>Fridericia connata</i>
			<i>Fridericia galba</i>
			<i>Fridericia heliota</i>
			<i>Fridericia isseli</i>
			<i>Fridericia nemoralis</i>
			<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>
			<i>Fridericia ratzeli</i>
			<i>Fridericia sohlenii</i>
			<i>Fridericia striata</i>
			<i>Fridericia sylvatica</i>
			<i>Fridericia tuberosa</i>
			-
		<i>Henlea</i>	<i>Henlea andreae</i>
			<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>
			-
		<i>Marionina</i>	<i>Marionina clavata</i>
			<i>Marionina communis</i>
			<i>Marionina filiformis</i>
			-
		<i>Mesenchytraeus</i>	<i>Mesenchytraeus armatus</i>
			-
		<i>Oconnorella</i>	<i>Oconnorella cambrensis</i>
			<i>Oconnorella tubifera</i>
Tubificida	Naididae	<i>Rhyacodrilus</i>	<i>Rhyacodrilus falciformis</i>

Table S3. Annelida taxa uniquely detected by the Olig01 or 18S primers.

Taxa detected using Olig01, but not using 18S	Taxa detected using 18S, but not using Olig01
<i>Achaeta bifollicula</i>	<i>Achaeta affinis</i>
<i>Achaeta bohemica</i>	<i>Aeolosoma</i>
<i>Achaeta brevivasa</i>	<i>Hormogaster</i>
<i>Achaeta unibulba</i>	<i>Marionina argentea</i>
<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea icterica</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea limicola</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea nocturna</i>	
<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	
<i>Bimastos rubidus</i>	
<i>Buchholzia appendiculata</i>	
<i>Chamaedrillus</i>	
<i>Cognettia chlorophila</i>	
<i>Dendrobaena octaedra</i>	
<i>Eisenia</i>	
<i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i>	
<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>	
<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	
<i>Enchytraeus dicaetus</i>	
<i>Enchytraeus norvegicus</i>	
<i>Enchytronia parva</i>	
<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>	
<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	
<i>Fridericia connata</i>	
<i>Fridericia galba</i>	
<i>Fridericia heliota</i>	
<i>Fridericia isseli</i>	
<i>Fridericia nemoralis</i>	
<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>	

<i>Fridericia ratzeli</i>	
<i>Fridericia sohlenii</i>	
<i>Fridericia striata</i>	
<i>Fridericia sylvatica</i>	
<i>Fridericia tuberosa</i>	
<i>Henlea andreae</i>	
<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>	
<i>Lumbricus castaneus</i>	
<i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>	
<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>	
<i>Marionina clavata</i>	
<i>Marionina communis</i>	
<i>Marionina filiformis</i>	
<i>Oconnorella cambrensis</i>	
<i>Oconnorella tubifera</i>	
<i>Rhyacodrilus falciformis</i>	
<i>Satchellius mammalis</i>	

Table S4. The detection of known Lumbricidae species per location based on the Olig01 primers according to the three different sampling protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

Location	Lumbricidae species	INBO_0_10	INBO_10_30	Lucas
Molenbeek	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>	x		
Molenbeek	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Lumbricus castaneus</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>			x
Burdinne	<i>Aporrectodea nocturna</i>		x	x
Burdinne	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x		x
Cerfontaine	<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	x		x
Genappe	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x		
Genappe	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	x	x	
Genappe	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>			x
Bredene	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i>	x		
Sombrefe	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x		x
Sombrefe	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x	x	
Sombrefe	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>		x	
Sombrefe	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	x		
Seneffe	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	x		x
Seneffe	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>	x		x
Seneffe	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>			x

Marke	<i>Aporrectodea nocturna</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>			x
Marke	<i>Bimastos rubidus</i>			x
Marke	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>	x	x	
Marke	<i>Satchellius mammalis</i>			x
Marke	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	x	x	x

Table S5. The detection of known Enchytraeidae species per location based on the Olig01 primers according to the three different sampling protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

Location	Enchytraeidae species	INBO_0_10	INBO_10_30	Lucas
Molenbeek	<i>Achaeta bohemica</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Achaeta unibulba</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Enchytraeus dichaeus</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia connata</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x		
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia sohlenii</i>			x
Molenbeek	<i>Fridericia sylvatica</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Marionina communis</i>	x		x
Diepenbeek	<i>Achaeta bifollicula</i>	x	x	x
Diepenbeek	<i>Cognettia chlorophila</i>	x		x
Diepenbeek	<i>Enchytraeus norvegicus</i>	x		x
Diepenbeek	<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Marionina clavata</i>	x	x	x
Diepenbeek	<i>Oconnorella cambrensis</i>	x	x	x
Diepenbeek	<i>Oconnorella tubifera</i>	x		
Burdinne	<i>Buchholzia fallax</i>		x	x
Burdinne	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	
Burdinne	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>		x	x
Burdinne	<i>Fridericia isseli</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x		

Cerfontaine	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>	x		x
Cerfontaine	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x		x
Cerfontaine	<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>	x		
Cerfontaine	<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>	x		
Genappe	<i>Buchholzia fallax</i>		x	x
Genappe	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Enchytraeus lacteus</i>	x	x	
Genappe	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x		x
Genappe	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Fridericia isseli</i>	x	x	
Genappe	<i>Fridericia ratzeli</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Fridericia sylvatica</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Fridericia tuberosa</i>			x
Bredene	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Enchytraeus lacteus</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Fridericia ratzeli</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Henlea andreae</i>	x		x
Bredene	<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>	x		
Sombrefte	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>	x	x	x
Sombrefte	<i>Enchytraeus bulbosus</i>	x	x	x
Sombrefte	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x	x	
Sombrefte	<i>Enchytraeus lacteus</i>	x		x
Sombrefte	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	x
Sombrefte	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x	x	x
Sombrefte	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>	x	x	x

Sombreffe	<i>Fridericia isseli</i>	x	x	x
Sombreffe	<i>Fridericia nemoralis</i>		x	x
Sombreffe	<i>Fridericia tuberosa</i>			x
Seneffe	<i>Enchytraeus buchholzi</i>		x	
Seneffe	<i>Enchytraeus christenseni</i>	x	x	
Seneffe	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>	x		x
Seneffe	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x		x
Seneffe	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Fridericia ratzeli</i>	x		
Seneffe	<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Fridericia christeri</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Fridericia galba</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Fridericia heliota</i>		x	
Marke	<i>Fridericia isseli</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Fridericia paroniana</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Henlea perpusilla</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Mesenchytraeus armatus</i>	x		

Table S6. Overview of all Collembola taxa detected using the Collembola-specific primers (Coll01). Empty cells inherit taxonomic classification from above; dash (-) represents unresolved identification.

Order	Family	Genus	Species	
Entomobryomorpha	Entomobryidae	<i>Coecobrya</i>	<i>Coecobrya tenebricosa</i>	
			<i>Dicranocentrus</i>	-
			<i>Entomobrya</i>	<i>Entomobrya lanuginosa</i>
				-
			<i>Heteromurus</i>	<i>Heteromurus nitidus</i>
				-
			<i>Lepidocyrtus</i>	-
			<i>Orchesella</i>	<i>Orchesella cincta</i>
				<i>Orchesella villosa</i>
				-
			<i>Willowsia</i>	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>
				-
			Isotomidae	<i>Cryptopygus</i>
			<i>Desoria</i>	<i>Desoria tigrina</i>
				-
			<i>Folsomia</i>	<i>Folsomia candida</i>
			<i>Isotoma</i>	<i>Isotoma viridis</i>
			<i>Isotomurus</i>	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>
			<i>Parisotoma</i>	-
			<i>Scutisotoma</i>	-
		Paronellidae	<i>Cyphoderus</i>	-
		Tomoceridae	<i>Pogonognathellus</i>	<i>Pogonognathellus flavescens</i>
				-
		<i>Tomocerus</i>	<i>Tomocerus jilinensis</i>	
			<i>Tomocerus nigrus</i>	
Neelipleona	Neelidae	<i>Megalothorax</i>	<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	
			<i>Megalothorax minimus</i>	
			<i>Megalothorax</i> sp EA010038	
			<i>Megalothorax</i> sp EA040003	
			<i>Megalothorax</i> sp EA040004-cs23	

			<i>Megalothorax sp EA040005-cs3</i>
			<i>Megalothorax sp EA040010</i>
			<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>
			-
Poduomorpha	Brachystomellidae	<i>Brachystomella</i>	-
	Hypogastruridae	<i>Ceratophysella</i>	-
		<i>Hypogastrura</i>	<i>Hypogastrura vernalis</i>
	Neanuridae	<i>Friesea</i>	-
		<i>Neanura</i>	<i>Neanura muscorum</i>
	Onychiuridae	<i>Protaphorura</i>	<i>Protaphorura armata</i>
	Tullbergiidae	<i>Mesaphorura</i>	-
		<i>Tullbergia</i>	-
Symphyleona	Arrhopalitidae	<i>Pygmarrhopalites</i>	-
	Dicyrtomidae	<i>Dicyrtomina</i>	<i>Dicyrtomina saundersi</i>
		<i>Ptenothrix</i>	-
	Sminthuridae	<i>Allacma</i>	<i>Allacma fusca</i>
		<i>Lipothrix</i>	<i>Lipothrix lubbocki</i>
		<i>Sminthurus</i>	<i>Sminthurus viridis</i>
	Sminthurididae	<i>Sminthurides</i>	-

Table S7. *Collembola* taxa uniquely detected by the Coll01 or 18S primers.

Taxa detected using Coll01, but not using 18S	Taxa detected using 18S, but not using Coll01
<i>Allacma fusca</i>	<i>Onychiurus hangchowensis</i>
<i>Brachystomella</i>	<i>Papirinus prodigiosus</i>
<i>Ceratophysella</i>	<i>Pseudosinella alba</i>
<i>Coecobrya tenebricosa</i>	<i>Xenylla grisea</i>
<i>Cryptopygus</i>	
<i>Cyphoderus</i>	
<i>Desoria tigrina</i>	
<i>Dicranocentrus</i>	
<i>Entomobrya lanuginosa</i>	
<i>Hypogastrura vernalis</i>	
<i>Isotoma viridis</i>	
<i>Lipothrix lubbocki</i>	
<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	
<i>Megalothorax minimus</i>	
<i>Megalothorax sp EA010038</i>	
<i>Megalothorax sp EA040003</i>	
<i>Megalothorax sp EA040004-cs23</i>	
<i>Megalothorax sp EA040005-cs3</i>	
<i>Megalothorax sp EA040010</i>	
<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	
<i>Mesaphorura</i>	
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	
<i>Parisotoma</i>	
<i>Pogonognathellus flavescens</i>	
<i>Protaphorura armata</i>	
<i>Ptenothrix</i>	
<i>Pygmarrhopalites</i>	
<i>Scutisotoma</i>	

Table S8. The detection of known Collembola species per location based on the Coll01 primers according to the three different sampling protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

Location	Species	INBO_0_10	INBO_10_30	Lucas
Molenbeek	<i>Isotoma viridis</i>	x		
Molenbeek	<i>Coecobrya tenebricosa</i>	x	x	x
Molenbeek	<i>Folsomia candida</i>	x		x
Diepenbeek	<i>Orchesella cincta</i>	x	x	
Diepenbeek	<i>Dicyrtomina saundersi</i>	x	x	x
Diepenbeek	<i>Tomocerus nigrus</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Megalothorax minimus</i>	x		x
Diepenbeek	<i>Orchesella villosa</i>			x
Diepenbeek	<i>Pogonognathellus flavescens</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Lipothrix lubbocki</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Folsomia candida</i>	x		
Burdinne	<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	x	x	x
Burdinne	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>	x	x	
Burdinne	<i>Protaphorura armata</i>	x	x	
Burdinne	<i>Megalothorax sp EA040004-cs23</i>		x	
Burdinne	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>	x		
Burdinne	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Isotoma viridis</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>	x		x
Cerfontaine	<i>Sminthurus viridis</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	x	x	x
Genappe	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>		x	
Genappe	<i>Protaphorura armata</i>		x	
Genappe	<i>Megalothorax sp EA040004-cs23</i>		x	
Genappe	<i>Heteromurus nitidus</i>	x	x	
Genappe	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>		x	
Bredene	<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	x	x	x
Bredene	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>	x	x	x
Bredene	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	x		

Sombreffe	<i>Desoria tigrina</i>	x		
Sombreffe	<i>Isotomurus maculatus</i>	x		
Sombreffe	<i>Megalothorax sp EA040010</i>		x	
Sombreffe	<i>Protaphorura armata</i>	x	x	x
Sombreffe	<i>Heteromurus nitidus</i>	x		
Sombreffe	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Isotoma viridis</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Orchesella cincta</i>			x
Marke	<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	x	x	
Marke	<i>Dicyrtomina saundersi</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Tomocerus nigrus</i>			x
Marke	<i>Megalothorax minimus</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Neanura muscorum</i>			x
Marke	<i>Megalothorax sp EA040010</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Pogonognathellus flavescens</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Megalothorax sp EA040003</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Heteromurus nitidus</i>		x	x
Marke	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Folsomia candida</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Tomocerus jilinensis</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Megalothorax sp EA010038</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Megalothorax incertus</i>	NA		x
Seneffe	<i>Entomobrya lanuginosa</i>	NA		x
Seneffe	<i>Megalothorax willemi</i>	NA		x
Seneffe	<i>Folsomia candida</i>	NA	x	x

Table S9. Overview of all Arthropoda taxa detected using the Arthropoda-specific primers (Inse01). Empty cells inherit taxonomic classification from above; dash (-) represents unresolved identification.

Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	
Arachnida	Araneae	Oxyopidae	-	-	
	Ixodida	Ixodidae	-	-	
	Mesostigmata	Digamasellidae	<i>Dendrolaelaps</i>	-	
		Discourellidae	-	-	
		Macrochelidae	<i>Macrocheles</i>	-	
			-	-	
		Macronyssidae	-	-	
		Parasitidae	<i>Parasitus</i>	-	
			-	-	
		Uropodidae	<i>Oodinychus</i>	<i>Oodinychus ovalis</i>	
			-	-	
		Varroidae	<i>Varroa</i>	-	
		Opiliones	Phalangidae	<i>Rilaena</i>	<i>Rilaena triangularis</i>
		Sarcoptiformes	-	-	-
Chilopoda	Geophilomorpha	Geophilidae	<i>Geophilus</i>	<i>Geophilus electricus</i>	
				<i>Geophilus truncorum</i>	
		Linotaeniidae	<i>Strigamia</i>	-	
			-	-	
		Scolopendromorpha	Cryptopidae	<i>Cryptops</i>	<i>Cryptops parisi</i>
Diplura	Diplura	Campodeidae	-	-	
Insecta	Coleoptera	Brentidae	<i>Nanophyes</i>	-	
		Cantharidae	<i>Lycocerus</i>	-	
			<i>Malthodes</i>	-	
		Carabidae	<i>Trechus</i>	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	
		Cerylonidae	-	-	
		Chrysomelidae	-	-	
		Coccinellidae	<i>Harmonia</i>	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	
		Curculionidae	<i>Barypeithes</i>	<i>Barypeithes araneiformis</i>	
				-	
			<i>Laparocerus</i>	-	

			<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>Otiorhynchus ovatus</i>
			<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>Polydrusus cervinus</i>
				-
			<i>Sitona</i>	<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>
		Elateridae	<i>Adrastus</i>	<i>Adrastus rachifer</i>
			<i>Agriotes</i>	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>
			<i>Athous</i>	<i>Athous haemorrhoidalis</i>
			<i>Denticollis</i>	<i>Denticollis linearis</i>
		Hydraenidae	<i>Ochthebius</i>	-
			-	-
		Hydrophilidae	<i>Cercyon</i>	-
		Lampyridae	-	-
		Leiodidae	<i>Nargus</i>	<i>Nargus algiricus</i>
		Lycidae	-	-
		Scarabaeidae	<i>Amphimallon</i>	<i>Amphimallon solstitiale</i>
		Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i>	<i>Othius subuliformis</i>
			<i>Tachyporus</i>	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>
		Tenebrionidae	<i>Nalassus</i>	<i>Nalassus laevioctostriatus</i>
	Diptera	Bibionidae	<i>Dilophus</i>	<i>Dilophus febrilis</i>
		Cecidomyiidae	<i>Campylomyza</i>	<i>Campylomyza flavipes</i>
			<i>Polyardis</i>	-
			<i>Sitodiplosis</i>	-
		Chironomidae	<i>Smittia</i>	-
			-	-
		Dolichopodidae	<i>Chrysotimus</i>	<i>Chrysotimus flaviventris</i>
			<i>Dolichopus</i>	<i>Dolichopus griseipennis</i>
		Empididae	<i>Hilara</i>	<i>Hilara maura</i>
			-	-
		Hybotidae	<i>Platypalpus</i>	-
		Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>	<i>Helina impuncta</i>
			<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Stomoxys calcitrans</i>
		Mycetophilidae	<i>Acnemia</i>	-
		Sciaridae	<i>Bradysia</i>	-

			<i>Corynoptera</i>	<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>
				-
			<i>Phytosciara</i>	-
		Tipulidae	<i>Tipula</i>	<i>Tipula varipennis</i>
	Hemiptera	Aphididae	<i>Rhopalosiphum</i>	<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i>
			-	-
		Cicadellidae	<i>Aphrodes</i>	<i>Aphrodes bicincta</i>
			<i>Eupteryx</i>	<i>Eupteryx gracilirama</i>
			-	-
		Pemphigidae	<i>Baizongia</i>	<i>Baizongia pistaciae</i>
			<i>Pemphigus</i>	-
			<i>Schlechtendalia</i>	-
			-	-
	Hymenoptera	Braconidae	-	-
		Formicidae	<i>Lasius</i>	<i>Lasius niger</i>
			-	-
		Ichneumonidae	-	-
		Tenthredinidae	<i>Nematus</i>	-
			-	-
	Lepidoptera	Adelidae	<i>Nematopogon</i>	<i>Nematopogon swammerdamellus</i>
	Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Chorthippus</i>	<i>Chorthippus parallelus parallelus</i>
			-	-
	Phthiraptera	-	-	-
	Siphonaptera	Ischnopsyllidae	-	-
		-	-	-
	Thysanoptera	Thripidae	<i>Thrips</i>	<i>Thrips hawaiiensis</i>
			-	-
Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Talitridae	-	-
	-	-	-	-

Table S10. *Arthropoda* orders uniquely detected by the Inse01 or 18S primers.

Orders detected using Inse01, but not using 18S	Orders detected using 18S, but not using Inse01
Hemiptera	Isopoda
Lepidoptera	Trombidiformes
Orthoptera	
Psocoptera	

Table S11 *Arthropoda families uniquely detected by the Inse01 or 18S primers.*

Families detected using Inse01, but not using 18S	Families detected using 18S, but not using Inse01
Acrididae	Acaridae
Adelidae	Alicorhagiidae
Aphididae	Phthiracaridae
Brentidae	Bimichaeliidae
Cantharidae	Brachychthoniidae
Carabidae	Calliphoridae
Chironomidae	Campodeidae
Cicadellidae	Chloropidae
Coccinellidae	Eniochthoniidae
Curculionidae	Eulohmanniidae
Dolichopodidae	Euphthiracaridae
Empididae	Eupodidae
Hybotidae	Eviphididae
Hydraenidae	Galumnidae
Hydrophilidae	Haplozetidae
Lampyridae	Histiostomatidae
Leiodidae	Hypochthoniidae
Muscidae	Keroplastidae
Mycetophilidae	Linopodidae
Pemphigidae	Nothridae
Scarabaeidae	Oribatulidae
Tenthredinidae	Palaeacaridae
Trogiidae	Phoridae
Uropodidae	Pteromalidae
Varroidae	Rhagidiidae
	Scheloribatidae
	Tectocephidae
	Tephritidae
	Trachytidae
	Trichoniscidae
	Veigaiidae

	Zerconidae
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Table S12. *Arthropoda* genera uniquely detected by the Inse0 or 18S primers.

Genera detected using Inse01, but not using 18S	Genera detected using 18S, but not using Inse01
<i>Acnemia</i>	<i>Acarus</i>
<i>Adrastus</i>	<i>Adelocera</i>
<i>Agriotes</i>	<i>Alicorhagia</i>
<i>Amphimallon</i>	<i>Alliphis</i>
<i>Aphrodes</i>	<i>Amischa</i>
<i>Athous</i>	<i>Aptinothrips</i>
<i>Baizongia</i>	<i>Atropacarus</i>
<i>Barypeithes</i>	<i>Bibio</i>
<i>Bradysia</i>	<i>Bimichaelia</i>
<i>Campylomyza</i>	<i>Camptomysia</i>
<i>Cercyon</i>	<i>Ceratitis</i>
<i>Cerobasis</i>	<i>Eniochthonius</i>
<i>Chorthippus</i>	<i>Eulohmannia</i>
<i>Chrysotimus</i>	<i>Galumna</i>
<i>Corynoptera</i>	<i>Gehypochthonius</i>
<i>Denticollis</i>	<i>Histiostoma</i>
<i>Dilophus</i>	<i>Hypochthonius</i>
<i>Dolichopus</i>	<i>Linopodes</i>
<i>Eupteryx</i>	<i>Liogluta</i>
<i>Harmonia</i>	<i>Lucilia</i>
<i>Helina</i>	<i>Mayetiola</i>
<i>Hilara</i>	<i>Naiadacarus</i>
<i>Lagria</i>	<i>Nothrus</i>
<i>Laparocerus</i>	<i>Orfelia</i>
<i>Lasius</i>	<i>Oribatula</i>
<i>Lycocerus</i>	<i>Otitesella</i>
<i>Malthodes</i>	<i>Palaeacarus</i>
<i>Nalassus</i>	<i>Phalangium</i>
<i>Nanophyes</i>	<i>Protoribates</i>
<i>Nargus</i>	<i>Pseudacteon</i>
<i>Nematopogon</i>	<i>Rhagidia</i>

<i>Nematus</i>	<i>Rhysotritia</i>
<i>Ochthebius</i>	<i>Sancassania</i>
<i>Oodinychus</i>	<i>Scheloribates</i>
<i>Othius</i>	<i>Sepedophilus</i>
<i>Otiorhynchus</i>	<i>Stigmatogaster</i>
<i>Parasitus</i>	<i>Tectocephus</i>
<i>Pemphigus</i>	<i>Thaumatomyia</i>
<i>Phosphaenus</i>	<i>Trachytes</i>
<i>Phytosciara</i>	<i>Trichoniscus</i>
<i>Platypalpus</i>	<i>Tyrophagus</i>
<i>Polyardis</i>	<i>Uloma</i>
<i>Polydrusus</i>	<i>Veigaia</i>
<i>Rhopalosiphum</i>	<i>Vulgarogamasus</i>
<i>Rilaena</i>	<i>Zatania</i>
<i>Schlechtendalia</i>	<i>Zercon</i>
<i>Sitodiplosis</i>	
<i>Sitona</i>	
<i>Smittia</i>	
<i>Stomoxys</i>	
<i>Strophosoma</i>	
<i>Tachyporus</i>	
<i>Thrips</i>	
<i>Trechus</i>	
<i>Varroa</i>	

Table S13. Arthropoda species uniquely detected by the Inse01 or 18S primers.

Species detected using Inse01, but not using 18S	Species detected using 18S, but not using Inse01
<i>Adrastus rachifer</i>	<i>Acarus siro</i>
<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	<i>Amischa nigrofusca</i>
<i>Amphimallon solstitiale</i>	<i>Aptinothrips rufus</i>
<i>Aphrodes bicincta</i>	<i>Atropacarus striculus</i>
<i>Athous haemorrhoidalis</i>	<i>Bibio longipes</i>
<i>Baizongia pistaciae</i>	<i>Camptomyia heterobia</i>
<i>Barypeithes araneiformis</i>	<i>Ceratitis capitata</i>
<i>Campylomyza flavipes</i>	<i>Cryptops hortensis</i>
<i>Cerobasis guestfalica</i>	<i>Cryptops parisi</i>
<i>Chorthippus parallelus parallelus</i>	<i>Eniochthonius minutissimus</i>
<i>Chrysotimus flaviventris</i>	<i>Eulohmannia ribagai</i>
<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>	<i>Galumna lanceata</i>
<i>Cryptops parisi</i>	<i>Geophilus alpinus</i>
<i>Denticollis linearis</i>	<i>Geophilus flavus</i>
<i>Dilophus febrilis</i>	<i>Hypochthonius rufulus</i>
<i>Dolichopus griseipennis</i>	<i>Linopodes motorius</i>
<i>Eupteryx gracilirama</i>	<i>Liogluta microptera</i>
<i>Geophilus alpinus</i>	<i>Lucilia sericata</i>
<i>Geophilus electricus</i>	<i>Mayetiola destructor</i>
<i>Geophilus truncorum</i>	<i>Naiadacarus arboricola</i>
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	<i>Nothrus silvestris</i>
<i>Helina impuncta</i>	<i>Orfelia fasciata</i>
<i>Hilara maura</i>	<i>Oribatula tibialis</i>
<i>Lagria hirta</i>	<i>Otitesella tsamvi</i>
<i>Lasius niger</i>	<i>Palaeacarus hystricinus</i>
<i>Nalassus laevioctostriatus</i>	<i>Phalangium opilio</i>
<i>Nargus algiricus</i>	<i>Protoribates hakonensis</i>
<i>Nematopogon swammerdamellus</i>	<i>Pseudacteon obtusus</i>
<i>Oodinychus ovalis</i>	<i>Rhysotritia duplicata</i>
<i>Othius subuliformis</i>	<i>Sancassania nesbitti</i>
<i>Otiorhynchus ovatus</i>	<i>Schelorbates ascendens</i>

<i>Phosphaenus hemipterus</i>	<i>Sepedophilus bipunctatus</i>
<i>Polydrusus cervinus</i>	<i>Strigamia crassipes</i>
<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i>	<i>Tectocephus velatus</i>
<i>Rilaena triangularis</i>	<i>Thaumatomyia notata</i>
<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>	<i>Trachytes baloghi</i>
<i>Stomoxys calcitrans</i>	<i>Trichoniscus pusillus</i>
<i>Strophosoma melanogrammum</i>	<i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i>
<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>	<i>Zatania albimaculata</i>
<i>Thrips hawaiiensis</i>	
<i>Tipula varipennis</i>	
<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	

Table S14. The detection of Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura, and Malacostraca species per location as detected by the Inse01 primers according to the three different sampling protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

Location	Species	INBO_0_10	INBO_10_30	Lucas
Bredene	<i>Dilophus febrilis</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Tipula varipennis</i>		x	
Bredene	<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Dolichopus griseipennis</i>	x		
Bredene	<i>Stomoxys calcitrans</i>			x
Bredene	<i>Aphrodes bicincta</i>			x
Burdinne	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	x		
Burdinne	<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>	x	x	
Cerfontaine	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	x	x	
Cerfontaine	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	x	x	x
Cerfontaine	<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>	x		x
Cerfontaine	<i>Chorthippus parallelus parallelus</i>			x
Cerfontaine	<i>Dolichopus griseipennis</i>			x
Diepenbeek	<i>Athous haemorrhoidalis</i>	x	x	
Diepenbeek	<i>Nalassus laevioctostriatus</i>	x	x	x
Diepenbeek	<i>Polydrusus cervinus</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Otiorhynchus ovatus</i>		x	
Diepenbeek	<i>Denticollis linearis</i>	x		
Diepenbeek	<i>Nematopogon swammerdamellus</i>			x
Diepenbeek	<i>Chrysotimus flaviventris</i>	x		
Genappe	<i>Pemphigus</i>		x	x
Genappe	<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>			x
Genappe	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>		x	x
Marke	<i>Lasius niger</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Cryptops parisi</i>	x		x
Marke	<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Tipula varipennis</i>	x		
Marke	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>			x

Marke	<i>Rilaena triangularis</i>			x
Marke	<i>Barypeithes araneiformis</i>	x	x	x
Marke	<i>Geophilus electricus</i>	x		x
Molenbeek	<i>Baizongia pistaciae</i>	x	x	
Molenbeek	<i>Corynoptera perpusilla</i>	x		
Molenbeek	<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>	x		x
Seneffe	<i>Amphimallon solstitiale</i>	x	x	
Seneffe	<i>Pemphigus</i>			x
Seneffe	<i>Lasius niger</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Tipula varipennis</i>	x		
Seneffe	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>	x	x	x
Seneffe	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>			x
Seneffe	<i>Hilara maura</i>		x	
Sombrefe	<i>Adrastus rachifer</i>		x	
Sombrefe	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	x	x	

Table S15. Species and genera uniquely detected in the forest floor per primer set: Olig01 Annelida (top), Coll01 Collembola (middle) and Inse01 Arthropoda (restricted to Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura and Malacostraca classes; bottom).

Location	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
Diepenbeek	Clitellata	Crassiclitellata	Lumbricidae	<i>Dendrobaena</i>	<i>Dendrobaena octaedra</i>
Diepenbeek	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Fridericia</i>	<i>Fridericia striata</i>
Diepenbeek	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Buchholzia</i>	<i>Buchholzia appendiculata</i>
Diepenbeek	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Fridericia</i>	<i>Fridericia bulboides</i>
Diepenbeek	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Mesenchytraeus</i>	<i>Mesenchytraeus armatus</i>
Gontrode	Clitellata	Crassiclitellata	Lumbricidae	<i>Bimastos</i>	<i>Bimastos rubidus</i>
Gontrode	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Marionina</i>	-
Diepenbeek	Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Entomobryidae	<i>Willowsia</i>	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>
Diepenbeek	Collembola	Symphyleona	Sminthuridae	<i>Allacma</i>	<i>Allacma fusca</i>
Diepenbeek	Collembola	Neelipleona	Neelidae	<i>Megalothorax</i>	<i>Megalothorax sp_EA040005-cs3</i>
Gontrode	Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Entomobryidae	<i>Orchesella</i>	<i>Orchesella cincta</i>
Gontrode	Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Entomobryidae	<i>Willowsia</i>	<i>Willowsia nigromaculata</i>
Gontrode	Collembola	Entomobryomorpha	Isotomidae	<i>Parisotoma</i>	-
Gontrode	Collembola	Symphyleona	Dicyrtomidae	<i>Dicyrtomina</i>	<i>Dicyrtomina saundersi</i>
Gontrode	Collembola	Poduromorpha	Neanuridae	<i>Neanura</i>	<i>Neanura muscorum</i>
Gontrode	Collembola	Poduromorpha	Tullbergiidae	<i>Mesaphorura</i>	-
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i>	<i>Othius subuliformis</i>
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Coleoptera	Leiodidae	<i>Nargus</i>	<i>Nargus algiricus</i>
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Cecidomyiidae	<i>Campylomyza</i>	<i>Campylomyza flavipes</i>
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Smittia</i>	-
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Empididae	<i>Hilara</i>	<i>Hilara maura</i>
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Hybotidae	<i>Platypalpus</i>	-
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Helina</i>	<i>Helina impuncta</i>
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Diptera	Sciaridae	<i>Phytosciara</i>	-
Diepenbeek	Insecta	Thysanoptera	Thripidae	<i>Thrips</i>	<i>Thrips hawaiiensis</i>
Diepenbeek	Chilopoda	Geophilomorpha	Geophilidae	<i>Geophilus</i>	<i>Geophilus truncorum</i>
Diepenbeek	Arachnida	Mesostigmata	Uropodidae	<i>Oodinychus</i>	<i>Oodinychus ovalis</i>
Gontrode	Insecta	Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Strophosoma</i>	<i>Strophosoma melanogrammum</i>

Gontrode	Insecta	Coleoptera	Elateridae	<i>Athous</i>	<i>Athous haemorrhoidalis</i>
Gontrode	Insecta	Coleoptera	Lampyridae	<i>Phosphaenus</i>	<i>Phosphaenus hemipterus</i>
Gontrode	Insecta	Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Lagria</i>	<i>Lagria hirta</i>
Gontrode	Insecta	Diptera	Hybotidae	<i>Platypalpus</i>	-
Gontrode	Chilopoda	Geophilomorpha	Geophilidae	<i>Geophilus</i>	<i>Geophilus truncorum</i>
Gontrode	Arachnida	Mesostigmata	Uropodidae	<i>Oodinychus</i>	<i>Oodinychus ovalis</i>

Figure S1. The number of Annelida species uniquely identified per location by both INBO protocols combined (left) and by the LUCAS protocol (right).

Figure S2. The number of Collembola species uniquely identified per location by both INBO protocols combined (left) and by the LUCAS protocol (right).

Figure S3. The number of Arthropoda species uniquely identified per location by both INBO protocols combined (left) and by the LUCAS protocol (right).

